

Breaking Boundaries: Police Brutality and the Racial Tensions in Pelotas' Immigrant Community

Rompiendo barreras: Brutalidad policial y las tensiones raciales en la comunidad inmigrante de Pelotas

Quebrando barreiras: Brutalidade policial e as tensões raciais na comunidade imigrante de Pelotas

Abstract

Between 2015 and 2017, the city of Pelotas, in the far south of Brazil, witnessed significant episodes of police violence against Senegalese immigrants. These incidents, captured on cell phones and widely shared online, generated substantial social outrage. Against this backdrop, the study aims to investigate the historical and social factors underpinning such brutal practices, which occur with greater regularity than they should. To this end, a mixed-method approach was employed, combining quantitative and historical qualitative analysis, semi-structured interviews, and statistical data. The findings highlight Pelotas' slaveholding past, whose legacy remains evident in the local daily manifestations of racism. The sudden and significant arrival of African immigrants with dark skin, freely and autonomously, for the first time in the city's history, revealed a disruption of implicit norms governing the presence of certain bodies in public spaces. This led to social tensions, particularly between public security forces and the immigrants. It is possible to conclude that these tensions likely triggered occurrences of police brutality, reflecting resistance to the symbolic redistribution of urban spaces and the question of who is allowed to occupy them. Thus, these unfortunate episodes not only reiterate historical inequalities but, above all, make clear the discomfort with shifts in racial and class dynamics in the city of Pelotas.

Keywords: Senegalese; police violence; international immigration; South-South immigration; racism, slavery, historical methodology.

Resumen

Entre 2015 y 2017, la ciudad de Pelotas, en el extremo sur de Brasil, fue escenario de notables episodios de violencia policial contra inmigrantes senegaleses. Las escenas, grabadas con teléfonos móviles y ampliamente difundidas online, generaron una gran conmoción social. De este contexto surge el objeto de estudio que busca investigar los impactos históricos y sociales que sustentan prácticas tan brutales con mayor regularidad de la que deberían. Para ello se utilizó un enfoque metodológico mixto, combinando análisis históricos cuantitativos y cualitativos, entrevistas semiestructuradas y datos estadísticos. Los resultados resaltan el pasado de esclavitud de Pelotas, con sus marcas aún presentes en el racismo local cotidiano. La repentina y significativa llegada de inmigrantes africanos de piel oscura, de forma libre y autónoma, por primera vez en la historia de la ciudad, puso de relieve una ruptura con las normas implícitas que regulan la presencia de determinados cuerpos en los espacios públicos. Como resultado, se crearon tensiones sociales, principalmente entre las fuerzas de seguridad pública y los inmigrantes. Es posible concluir que tales tensiones posiblemente desencadenaron incidentes de brutalidad policial, que reflejan resistencia a la redistribución simbólica de los espacios urbanos y por quiénes pueden ser ocupados estos espacios. Por tanto, los lamentables episodios no sólo reiteran

desigualdades históricas, sino que sobre todo dejan en evidencia el malestar con el cambio de patrones raciales y de clases en la ciudad de Pelotas.

Palabras clave: senegalés; violencia policial; inmigración internacional; inmigración sur-sur; racismo, esclavitud, metodología histórica.

Resumo

Entre 2015 e 2017, a cidade de Pelotas, no extremo sul do Brasil, foi palco de episódios marcantes de violência policial contra imigrantes senegaleses. As cenas, registradas em celulares e amplamente divulgadas online, geraram grande comoção social. A partir desse contexto surge o objeto de estudo que busca investigar os impactos históricos e sociais que sustentam tais práticas de brutalidade com maior regularidade dos que deveriam. Para isso, foi utilizada aposta metodológica mista, combinando análise quantitativa e qualitativa histórica, entrevistas semiestruturadas e dados estatísticos. Os resultados destacam o passado escravagista de Pelotas, com suas marcas ainda presentes no racismo local diário. A chegada repentina e em número significativo de imigrantes africanos, de pele retinta, de forma livre e autônoma, pela primeira vez na história da cidade, evidenciou um rompimento com normas implícitas que regulam a presença de determinados corpos em espaços públicos. Com isso, tensões sociais foram criadas, principalmente entre as forças de segurança pública e os imigrantes. É possível concluir que possivelmente tais tensões desencadearam as ocorrências de brutalidade policial, que refletem uma resistência à redistribuição simbólica dos espaços urbanos e por quem esses espaços podem ser ocupados. Sendo assim, os infelizes episódios não somente reiteram desigualdades históricas, mas acima de tudo deixam claro o incômodo com a mudança nos padrões de raça e classe na cidade de Pelotas.

Palavras-chave: Senegaleses; violência policial; imigração internacional; imigração sul-sul; racismo, escravidão, metodologia histórica.

Introduction

In the context of International Migrations, increasing attention has been directed to the Global South, particularly to South-South migrations. It is within this conjuncture that the theme of the present research is situated. The discussions generated by the mainstream media lead us to believe that the important debate should revolve around global South-North migration, as there is a supposed “invasion” of underdeveloped citizens entering their territories.

However, reality could not be more different, as clearly demonstrated by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) in its Global Trends: Forced Displacement in 2022. The report shows that at least 70 per cent of refugees

and other people in need of international protection lived in neighboring countries, and that 76 per cent of these hosting countries were low- or mid-income countries (UNHCR, p. 2, 2023).

When it comes to understanding, scientifically studying, and elucidating a social science topic that is inherently multidisciplinary, it is necessary to go beyond surface observations. As Erin D. Phelps states, “I’ve become convinced that in order to understand what migration looks like in a globalized world, SSM is key. Ignoring SSM is ignoring nearly half of the big picture of global migration” (p. 2, 2014).

In this sense, it can be classified as an intersection of the Sociology of Violence, International Migrations, History, and Race. This study analyzes cases of police brutality against Senegalese immigrants in a mid-sized city in southern Brazil, occurring between the years 2015 and 2017. For methodological reasons, the cases were divided into three groups, which will be further explained later.

The cases occurred in Pelotas, a mid-sized city with a strong university and tourist character, known for its historic center, which features buildings dating from the early 19th to early 20th century, along with emerging investment in rural tourism. Its economy is currently based on local commerce, the real estate market—primarily driven by the universities, with the constant arrival and departure of students—and, finally, a weakened and diminished industrial community, primarily characterized by civil construction and rice processing.

Located on the margins of the Laguna dos Patos to the east, bordered by the São Gonçalo Canal to the south, and about an hour's drive southwest from the border with Uruguay, Pelotas's economy relies significantly on commerce. As expected, it has a central area where shops, restaurants, and local businesses are concentrated. This area sells a wide range of goods, including clothing, cell phones, home

appliances, furniture, coffee shops, restaurants, bars, and more. In Brazil, such areas are commonly referred to as a *calçadão*. This space holds symbolic significance for the city, as it is where everything happens. People gather there to chat; couples arrange dates; coworkers or families go for lunch; friends meet for coffee and to catch up, and so on.

It was within this setting, unmistakably noticed by local residents, that Senegalese immigrants began arriving in Pelotas in 2013. The state of Rio Grande do Sul, where Pelotas is located, is part of southern Brazil, a region composed of Paraná, Santa Catarina, and Rio Grande do Sul. This region was historically used as a racial whitening project (*embranquecimento racial*) (Hogbauer, 2003; Seyferth, 1990) and, as such, received a large number of European immigrants, primarily from Italy, Germany, Poland, France, and Ukraine, along with smaller groups from other ethnicities and nationalities, such as Finns and Dutch.

As a result, the inhabitants of Pelotas, a city where 11.8% of the population identifies as Black (IBGE, 2022), experienced a significant visual impact with the arrival of Senegalese immigrants—mostly men, dark-skinned, and of tall stature. This impact was felt even among local residents descended from enslaved people, whose skin tones today are generally lighter. One of the interviewees for this research, referred to here as *Érica*¹, to protect her anonymity for ethical reasons, is a Black woman approximately 50 years old, born and raised in Pelotas, and a prominent figure in the local Black social movement. She emphasizes: “This is about a local issue—they are dark-skinned African immigrants, tall in stature, and they physically stand out. The city, everyone, when they see them, even being Black—and we do have Black people in the city—they know these people are not from here.”

¹ Interview conducted on November 27, 2024.

The administrative records of the National Committee for Refugees (CONARE)² attest to the veracity of the situation. Having been established in 1999, when it received only about 99 asylum requests, by 2018, it received nearly 80,000. According to Rosana Baeninger (2019), in addition to the clear contribution of Haitian migration following the 2010 disasters, it is important to highlight that during the same period, the growth rate of asylum requests from Africans was 25.42% per year. However, “an important increase in the flow is observed starting in 2013, when the number of requests surpasses a thousand per year, peaking at 6,000 in 2014 and 2017” (p. 48, 2019), with one of the main nationalities responsible for this increase being Senegalese, as the country accounts for almost 28% of the asylum requests from Africans received by the UNHCR (until 1997) and CONARE (since 1997) in Brazil.

Theoretical framework

There is no way to address International Migration effectively without doing so in a multidisciplinary manner. Therefore, authors such as Mário Osório Magalhães (2011; 2012; 2017), Nicolau Drey (1839), Maria Eunice Madeira (1989), Ester Judite Bondjouya Gutierrez (2004), Carmen Rejane Flores Wizniewzky (2001), Dario Scott (2017), Jonas Moreira Vargas (2014; 2016), and Lia Osório Moreira (2005) would be crucial in making this research capable of explaining and exploring the historical context of the city. Above all, this research deals with the local, a case study that took place in three parts at a specific location, in both space and time. Without the work of historians, it would be impossible to understand what occurred.

Delving into the specific scenario of International Migrations, particularly those relevant in this context, the South-South migrations, Erin Phelps (2014) was

² CONARE is the Brazilian national body responsible for adjudicating asylum requests in Brazil.

fundamental for the progress of the research. However, without losing focus on South-South migration, but rather within a more national context and even historical migration, the works of Giralda Seyferth (1990), Rosana Baeninger (2019), and Andreas Hofbauer (2003) are invaluable.

As for the issue of violence, Egon Bittner (1970) lays the foundation for us to understand the context of the cases analyzed, but Loïc Wacquant (2009) and Didier Fassin (2013) are essential for understanding the reflections and motivations behind police violence against migrants and lower-class populations. Finally, Ana Beatriz Loner (1999) and Caiuá Cardoso Al-Alam (2007) are crucial for understanding that the violence studied here is not only directed at migrant and lower-class bodies, but also bears a very specific racial marking.

Methodology

Considering the importance of geographically and historically situating a case study research to be analyzed competently, as well as in line with the multidisciplinary nature of International Migrations, a mixed methodology was chosen for the best elucidation of the research.

At first, an essentially historical methodology (Lucas, 1985) is employed, with a thorough analysis of the history of the city of Pelotas and its mesoregion. We then proceed through the history of the city's formation and its cultural and economic significance for the southern region of Brazil, as well as for Brazil as a whole. From this point, we arrive at a moment where we explain in detail how Pelotas' economy was built, largely with slave labor. Not only that, we also demonstrate the harmful effects of this historical period on the racial segregation in the city that persists to this day.

Furthermore, a quantitative methodology (Plonsey et al., 2007) was also used, demonstrating the continuous and progressive importance of the academic production on South-South migration flows, using data from UNHCR (2023) and CONARE (2019). Additionally, statistical data from IBGE (2022) was used to show the percentage of the black population in Pelotas, as well as from APERS, with historical data compiled between 1850 and 1890.

As is customary in any social science research, a bibliographic review methodology (Ocaña-Fernández; Fuster-Guillén, 2021) was used, as it is an essential tool for analyzing the research objects within our scientific field. There is no other way to understand social theories, interpret the cases we are studying, and, ultimately, arrive at robust conclusions without grounding them in a serious scientific method. The bibliographic review is the tool that provides this support

Finally, the research method of in-depth interviews (Della Porta, 2014) was also used. Unfortunately, it was not possible to interview the Senegalese victims of police brutality, as when attempting to locate them, this researcher was informed by the small number of Senegalese still residing in Pelotas that they had all left the city in search of a more welcoming place where they could carry out their work without police intervention. However, I succeeded in interviewing two representative figures from the city's Black movement. One is a Black man, currently around 40 years old, who at the time of the violent incidents was involved with the Municipal Council for the Participation and Development of the Black Community of Pelotas, and who even participated in the legal and political defense of the immigrants during the incidents. The other is a Black woman, around 50 years old, with strong involvement in the Black cultural scene in Pelotas, a former teacher in the public education system, and a long-time municipal public servant.

Results

First, it is necessary to understand the geographical specificity of the Pelotas region. It is from this information that it will be possible to comprehend characteristics that are found only in this mesoregion. After all, by understanding its past and the circumstances of its formation, one can understand the place we are dealing with.

There are three cases of police violence against African immigrants from Senegal that this thesis will focus on. Therefore, it is crucial to deeply understand the context in which these events occurred and their characteristics. Perhaps this will bring us closer to a full understanding of the research problem. During the confrontations between immigrants and state forces, various actors were involved. The analysis proposed here will also contribute to discerning the local historical context that shaped the culture and mentality of the people involved in the events: whether they were municipal guards, bystanders who witnessed the acts, or public servants from the Urban Mobility Secretariat of the city of Pelotas. To some extent, while the study of Pelotas' history may not fully capture the cultural and mentalities of the Senegalese immigrants, it can at least extend to the local context in which they were inserted at the time of the police encounters.

I can begin telling the story of my city starting from 1758. Currently, the city has 325,689 (three hundred twenty-five thousand, six hundred eighty-nine) inhabitants, according to the 2022 census by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE). Forged from a slave-based economy, the city reached its economic peak between the 1860s and 1890s, with the charque industry. Becoming one of the

most important cities in the southern part of the country, it stood out as a commercial center and exporter of meat and leather (Magalhães, 2012).

On July 7, 1812, the city was elevated to the status of a parish³, and it was given the name São Francisco de Paula. This date is celebrated as the city's anniversary, as it marks the beginning of its official history. As mentioned earlier, it was in 1758 that Colonel Tomás Luís Osorio received the first "sesmaria" (land grant) of Pelotas. The municipality today is situated in the area that, by the end of the 18th century, was covered by five "estâncias" (landholdings). The one granted to Tomás is the oldest (Magalhães, 2011).

Upon deeper reflection, it does not seem fair or intellectually pertinent to speak of the beginning of a city's history (and consequently its people and their history) solely from the moment it received⁴ this territory from a colonel, who was then tasked with its administration and protection, much less from its elevation to the administrative category considered sufficiently important in a period when the country was still colonized by a European nation.

The aforementioned parish of Pelotas was bounded by the São Gonçalo Canal and the Santa Barbara Stream, territories that were once owned by Manuel Carvalho de Souza. He, like Tomás Luís Osorio, received a land grant, the so-called Monte Bonito, in 1779. However, it is important to highlight the figure of Luiz Gonçalves Viana, who, without any title or decree conferring ownership over the Rincão de Pelotas, "despite not being the earliest grantee, can be considered the first of Pelotas' colonizers" (Magalhães, 2011).

³ In Portugal and the former Portuguese Empire, a "freguesia" represented the smallest administrative unit. During the period of the Brazilian Empire, the territories of the neutral municipality, which was the imperial seat, were organized into divisions called "freguesias." Within the city, these subdivisions were known as "freguesias de dentro" (inner parishes), while those located in the peripheral areas were called "freguesias de fora da cidade" (outer parishes) (Sant'Anna; Mizuta, 2010).

⁴ According to a dispatch by Gomes Freire de Andrade, commander-general of the southern captaincies, the land grant received by Colonel Tomás was a donation (Magalhães, 2011).

It is important to emphasize that in 1777, José Pinto Martins, a migrant fleeing the drought that afflicted the Captaincy of Ceará, founded, three years later in 1779, the first *charqueada*⁵ in the region, along the banks of the Arroio Pelotas. Soon, various portions of the *sesmarias* or *Rincões* were divided and redistributed. This is detailed by Mário Osório Magalhães (2011), who recounts how Manuel Carvalho de Souza had little time to consider himself the owner of his land portions, as it was not long before he alienated an area of five and one-third leagues. These lands, in turn, were also passed on and subdivided into smaller plots, referred to as *datas* at the time. Consequently, the number of landowners steadily increased.

One of the landowners, Mrs. Maria Eufrása da Silveira⁶, sister of Isabel Francisca—both widows of captains-major of Rio Grande—made donations for the establishment of the village. Notably and relevantly, these lands are currently part of the areas where Praça Coronel Pedro Osório, the Pelotas City Hall, and the Pelotas Public Library are located⁷. (Magalhães, 2011).

The Slaved Past

It is unsurprising that a city with this description, located in the Global South and during the historical period under discussion, would be deeply marked by social stratifications. Later, we will delve into the period strongly defined by the *Charqueadas* Era in Pelotas. However, when examining the city during the mid-to-late 19th century, its population increased exponentially. According to Jonas Moreira Vargas, "In 1858, the [municipality] had 12,883 inhabitants; by 1872, it exceeded

⁵ *Charqueadas* were establishments dedicated to the preparation of salted meat and its derivatives. The cattle were slaughtered in the so-called *mangueira de matança* (slaughter corral) (Couty, 2000).

⁶ "Among other assets she acquired, the esteemed lady owned almost the entire southern area of the current city..." (Magalhães, p. 19, 2011).

⁷ An important site in the city's historical and tourist landscape, as it was once home to influential families of the 19th and 20th centuries, who economically and politically shaped and molded the region. This area also houses Pelotas' theaters and public market.

25,000 and, in 1890, reached 41,591 residents" (p. 133, 2016). The explanation for the city's explosive growth lies in the exploitation of enslaved labor.

I cannot write this work without addressing a period that, in certain contexts (perhaps excessively so), has been regarded as a time of glory for the far south of Rio Grande do Sul and southern Brazil as a whole—the economic heyday of the Charqueadas period⁸ in the pampas region of Rio Grande do Sul. From the perspective of this author, little glory can be discerned in this historical period beyond its economic outcomes. The labor that executed and, above all, sustained the charque-making industry's power did not come from the Barons of Charque, nor from their families, but from enslaved Black hands, forcibly brought to Brazil through a coerced migratory process.

It is our duty as researchers in the Social Sciences (not solely Historians or scholars directly engaged with this topic) to ensure that this past is not forgotten and that the horrors these individuals endured are not erased. We are addressing forced labor, international abduction (what we would now term Trafficking in Persons⁹), starvation, physical and psychological violence, torture, and other afflictions as far-reaching as the human imagination can conceive.

Considering that the southern region of Brazil, in the mid-17th century, was regarded as the most significant source of beef production in the country (Dreys, 1839), we turn our attention to the figure of José Pinto Martins. A Portuguese man originating from the European mainland rather than the islands belonging to Portugal,

⁸ which occurred between approximately 1822 and 1860, spanning about forty years (Vargas, 2014).

⁹ According to the United Nations Convention Against Transnational Organized Crime and the Protocols Thereto, from 2000, "Trafficking in Persons" shall mean the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring, or receipt of persons, by means of the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation. Exploitation shall include, at a minimum, the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labor or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude, or the removal of organs.

he departed from Ceará (in northern Brazil) in 1777 due to the severe drought afflicting the region at that time and established what is believed to be the first charqueada in Pelotas in 1779.

In fact, we are discussing a figure who identified the ideal conditions to replicate a new industrial economic model (also referred to as the saladeril industry) in a region that already possessed an abundance of raw materials for his product (Magalhães, 2017).

The charqueadas were entrepreneurial structures where salted dried meat (carne de sol) was produced. As previously noted in a footnote, cattle were slaughtered in what was then called the mangueira de matança (slaughtering corral). Ester Gutierrez (2017) provides a more detailed explanation of how the processes unfolded in this site of hecatomb:

This structure was a corral with high and sturdy walls, capable of holding up to 60 head of cattle. It was connected by a narrow pathway, the brete. The floor was sloped and slippery, usually made of large bricks. A platform ran along the exterior of the slaughter corral. From there, an enslaved individual would throw a lasso over the ox that appeared in the brete. The other end of the same lasso, coiled around a winch, was secured to the harness of two pack animals. The lasso was pulled; the ox was dragged, and its head was fixed against the winch. A second enslaved person, known as the butcher or "neck breaker," would thrust a large knife into the nape of the ox's neck. The animal would collapse onto the wagon. Two enslaved individuals then pulled the wagon carrying the animal to the cancha, located on one or both sides of the tracks. There, dragged by two enslaved individuals on foot or by one on horseback, the ox was toppled from the wagon, skinned, and then stabbed in the heart to bleed it out (Gutierrez, p. 65, 2017).

The process is brutal, obviously for the animals, but also for the men, who were covered in blood. After the bleeding process, the more prized parts of the freshly slaughtered animal were directed to a place resembling a warehouse, while the more

common cuts were designated for the slaves' food. Finally, the organs and parts with no use were thrown into the bodies of water along the Charqueadas (Gutierrez, 2017).

Beyond the brutality towards the animals, there is the brutality of class division and the process of slavery itself. Reflecting on the history of the Black population in Pelotas means revisiting the contributions of men and women who, subjected to slavery, worked in charqueadas, brickworks, farms, and urban environments, often facing degrading and inhumane conditions. For many, work in the region's charqueadas was seen as punishment, designated for those accused of crimes, offenses, or acts of insubordination (Al-Alam, 2007).

It is known that a large portion of the Black population was introduced to the region with the establishment of the charqueadas. Although there had been slavery here before, it was with the development of the charqueadas that slaves were forcibly brought to the area in large numbers. To build the charqueadas themselves, the mansions, the large buildings, everything that today's high society in Pelotas takes pride in and fails to recognize the Black labor that was involved (Loner, 1999).

Similarly, the prisoners of the time, such as those held at the House of Correction of the Village of São Francisco de Paula, were part of this system. The prison was built next to the Arroio Pelotas, for reasons we may never fully know, but it is clear that it was constructed in that location. There, various figures, including those excluded by others, such as slaves, poor people, and generally those viewed unfavorably by society, frequented it—"a focus of immorality and a gathering place for Creoles and entertainment for slaves" (Gutierrez, p. 205, 2004).

During the Brazilian Imperial period, Pelotas stood out as the largest producer of charque, not only in Rio Grande do Sul but in all of Brazil. Its privileged geographical position, between the port of Rio Grande and an extensive region of

pastureland suited for cattle raising, greatly favored this scenario. The city housed the most modern *charqueadas* of the province, which attracted numerous investors and resulted in a large concentration of enslaved labor on properties dedicated to production (Vargas, 2014).

Do not forget the economic description I make of the city of Pelotas at the beginning of the article, which was only minimally industrialized. There is a reason for this, as the economic peak of the region occurred mid- to late 19th century, especially with the enslaved labor that was only abolished in Brazil on May 13, 1888. After the period of salting production, the southern region of Rio Grande do Sul entered a period of economic stagnation.

Worksheet 1 – Profile of the assets of the deceased in Pelotas (1850-1890) (%)

	Rural Properties	Urban Properties	Money	Active Debts	Shares	Slaves	Animals	Passive Debts	Total Estate
1850/55	40,5	11,8	11,6	19,5	0,7	7,9	6,4	0,8	25
1860/65	30,0	10,5	12,4	9,4	0,4	20,5	9,0	4,4	41
1870/75	32,4	21,1	6,0	14,4	1,9	10,3	11,1	2,5	65
1880/85	36,7	22,2	8,6	9,4	6,7	4,5	8,2	16,6	70
1890	40,3	26,5	7,2	12,1	6,1	-	0,9	10,2	55

Fonte: Inventários *post-mortem* dos cartórios de Pelotas (Post-mortem inventories from the notary offices of Pelotas) (APERS)

The importance of this historical period for the city and region is so prominent that it serves as a source of pride for its residents, especially the descendants of the elite of Pelotas at the time. Unfortunately, these individuals often have little understanding or recognition of the significance of the work performed by the Black population throughout history, as well as the contributions they made to the construction of the cultural and historical identity of the municipality. Furthermore, even today, the *charqueadas* are enjoyed as a form of tourist capital.

Pelotas is recognized as the National City of Sweets, with fairs and events specifically dedicated to celebrating and promoting this trade. Generally speaking, this culture is often relativized with the Portuguese colonization of the city (Ferreira; Cerqueira, 2007). However, it is necessary to revisit this origin, as much of the ancestry and contribution to the typical sweet recipes of Pelotas comes from enslaved women, as described by Marta Bonow Rodrigues (2015): "Black women, for the most part, performed activities related to domestic services, occupying roles such as cooking, ironing clothes, washing garments, sewing, and acting as wet nurses. In addition to these duties, many were assigned to work as 'slave women for profit,' being hired to sell sweets on trays throughout urban areas and also to serve as wet nurses.

In an interview with Ricardo¹⁰, a Black man, around 50 years old, and an activist in the Black movement of Pelotas, a case was shared with me that demonstrates the facets of racism and the legacy of slavery in Pelotas today. As this man stated:

I never forget, the Public Library building is next to the City Hall, and at one point, a few years ago, I was passing by and saw a lady with her little son, her grandson by the arm, showing him the entrance to the Public Library. I was coming down from the City Hall and I asked her, I said: "Go in there and show him, what you're showing him is beautiful, go in there and show him." She replied: "No, I don't think we can go in here." A Black lady, a Black boy. I said: "But why can't you enter a public building? You can and should go in. Show him." [...] She felt forbidden from entering with her grandson there, she was passing that down generationally, [author's name]. This is something very strong. We say this is a wound that's hard to heal.

¹⁰ Fictitious name, for ethical reasons and to avoid identifying the interviewee.

This account was very heavy and difficult to absorb after the interview. It required a period of reflection for me. I can only imagine what it's like for those who experience this on their own skin. Shortly after, in the interview, Ricardo also continues to share important lessons with me by saying...

Look, we are in the 21st century, and this symbolic power still operates there. So, observe, [author's name], the harmful effect of this symbolic power on bodies, how present it is in Brazilian society, especially in Pelotas, which is an exemplary locus for this kind of questioning you are making.

Some things are changing currently, with the city hall carrying out a historical work aimed at understanding the impact of slavery on the region, culturally, historically, and economically. It is certainly just the beginning, but it is a start, and one that needs to be made.

Discussion

Our cases

The first report of police violence against Senegalese immigrants in the city of Pelotas, Rio Grande do Sul, dates back to December 2, 2015, published by the local newspaper *Diário Popular*¹¹. It is important to note that on June 14, 2024, this news outlet ceased its operations. The incident occurred at the corner of Andrade Neves and Marechal Floriano Streets, in the city center, a location known as the "calçadão" of Pelotas. It is interesting to observe that there are three distinct state representations at this moment: public servants from the Municipal Secretariat of City Management and Urban Mobility (SGCMU), who initiate the inspection with the intent of seizing goods without legal provenance; the presence of the Municipal Guard to ensure the protection of these public servants; and, finally, with the escalation of tension, the

¹¹ https://www.diariopopular.com.br/index.php?n_sistema=3056&id_noticia=MTA2NTQy&id_area=Mg==

Military Police was called to the scene. According to the Diário Popular report, the goods sold by the immigrants were successfully seized, after which the civilian population present began chanting "give it back!". The immigrants then returned and attempted to recover their items from the public servants, at which point the confrontation began. What started with shoving and shouting escalated with the intervention of the bystanders, the arrival of the Military Police, reporters, and widespread commotion.

A video recorded by the Diário Popular reporting team can be found on YouTube¹². What stands out is the intense support from the population towards the immigrants, who ask the news team to document the injuries of the men. In the video, it is possible to see about nine Senegalese immigrants, young Black men speaking Portuguese with a strong accent. Two of them show their injuries and torn clothes to the journalistic camera that reports the incident. The Senegalese inform that they possess receipts for the products they are selling, although they are aware of the illegality of selling them in that location. Meanwhile, the inspectors report aggressive reactions from the immigrants when the seizures began and the conflicts ensued. A large number of people were taken to the Police Station for Immediate Attention (DPPA), including the immigrants themselves, municipal guards, military police officers, and civilians who wished to testify about the event.

On December 3, 2015, one day after this first incident, it was reported¹³ that the immigrants sought responses from the Public Authorities. With the support of GEMIGRA¹⁴, represented by Prof. Dr. Ana Paula Dittgen¹⁵ and Prof. Fábio

¹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H16j9SyB-A8>

¹³ https://www.diariopopular.com.br/index.php?n_sistema=3056&id_noticia=MTA2NTg3&id_area=Mg==

¹⁴ The Migration Policy and Human Rights Research Group (GEMIGRA) at the Catholic University of Pelotas (UCPEL) was established in 2013 as a project to encourage academic research at the undergraduate level by two professors from the UCPEL Law program, Prof. Dr. Ana Paula Dittgen and Prof. Dr. Anelize Maximila Correa. Initially, the group also provided pro bono legal assistance to immigrants, but over time a new group was created

Gonçalves¹⁶, in his capacity as President of the Pelotas Municipal Council for Participation and Development of the Black Community, went to the Public Prosecutor's Office and the Pelotas City Council to demand the return of the seized goods and to report the difficulties immigrants face in entering the formal labor market, as they are rejected in job interviews or offered very low-paying proposals. Soon after, GEMIGRA filed a criminal complaint action on behalf of the immigrants regarding the incident that occurred that week.

According to the timeline that can be constructed with the support of the news available online about the conflicts in question, it can be inferred that after a second brutal operation that gained significant attention in the city, the Pelotas Executive Power began negotiations to address the situation, which at this point had become delicate. This violent operation took place on June 9, 2016.

Operation launched on June 9, 2016. Photo no. 1.

Photos: Paulo Rossi, 2016. Source: Diário Popular Newspaper.

solely focused on providing legal services to immigrants and refugees, while GEMIGRA continued its original focus on academic research, mainly at the undergraduate level.

¹⁵ Professor of Constitutional and Agrarian Law at the Catholic University of Pelotas.

¹⁶ Currently a PhD candidate in Law at the Federal University of Santa Catarina, on a sandwich period at the National Autonomous University of Mexico, UNAM.

Operation launched on June 9, 2016. Photo no. 2.

Photos: Paulo Rossi, 2016. Source: Diário Popular Newspaper..

Operation launched on June 9, 2016. Photo no. 3.

Photos: Paulo Rossi, 2016. Source: Diário Popular Newspaper.

Prior to this operation, that is, between December 2, 2015, and June 9, 2016, there are no records of operations or conflicts between the Municipal Guard or the

inspectors from the Department of Urban Mobility and the immigrants. However, it remains unclear whether there was no record of such events or if it truly was a period of tranquility.

Regarding the operation launched in June 2016, although there is a post on Facebook by the Diário Popular newspaper¹⁷ it is not possible to find the news article on the local newspaper's website. Similarly, attempts to search for the news directly on the website have been unsuccessful.

On June 22, 2016, the Municipality of Pelotas, represented by Eduardo Leite, the city's then mayor, met with several interested parties to discuss a proposal for the future of the immigrant population in the city. The following representatives participated in the meeting: the University of Catholic Pelotas (UCPEL), Federal University of Pelotas (UFPEL), Brazilian Bar Association (OAB), Regional Police Department, Regional Council of Ostensive Police (CRPO-Sul), 4th Battalion of the Military Brigade (BPM), Federal Revenue, the "Cidade Bem Cuidada" program, the Secretariat of Social Justice, Security, and City and Urban Mobility Management, the Municipal Guard, and the Civil Defense.

From this proposal, the Immigrant Care Plan emerged, which was extensively addressed in an interview with public servant Aline Crochemore¹⁸. The Immigrant Care Plan¹⁹ was launched by the Pelotas City Hall on September 22, 2016, following meetings between the Pelotas Social Justice Secretariat and GEMIGRA, and, it is important to highlight, shortly after the second violent incident against immigrants, dated June 9, 2022. The program was divided into three main areas: social action,

¹⁷<https://www.facebook.com/diariopopularRS/posts/pfbid025vbfUhrYyCupBeZ3hiVvBdHcuWTySnFaERS9Y3RKjnHecYFwDK5PHAcDw7t9WjHl>

¹⁸ Interviewed on September 9, 2022.

¹⁹ More information about the Plan can be found in the following news article: <https://ucpel.edu.br/noticias/projeto-da-ucpel-e-alicerce-a-plano-de-atencao-aos-imigrantes-da-prefeitura-de-pelotas>. Accessed on September 28, 2022.

culture, and opportunities. According to data provided by the GEMIGRA group at the time, there were approximately hundreds Senegalese residing in the city, all men aged between 15 and 20, that is, young individuals. Speakers of the Wolof language, the vast majority worked in informal trade in the city center, while a minority were formally employed in the construction sector. It is therefore clear that the project's goal was the social integration of this group, in response to the conflicts between the public security sector and the Senegalese immigrant population.

Regarding the interview with public servant Aline Crochemore, she refers to the project using the term "Nucleus," explaining that the Public Administration proposed a pause in inspections, fully aware of the social vulnerability of the group targeted by the operations. This pause would allow for better social integration until the inspections resumed. According to Aline, the Nucleus included the Secretariats of Social Assistance (of which she herself was a part at the time), Urban Mobility, Human Rights, GEMIGRA, UFPEL (given the availability of Portuguese language classes for foreigners), the Guardianship Council, the Regional Education Coordination, and *Cáritas*. Aline coordinated the Nucleus and described some challenges in convincing immigrants to cease engaging in irregular street trade, including the fact that street commerce is part of their home country's culture and the income from such activities was higher than what was offered to the group through formalized work. Overall, she believes the project was successful, though she is unable to define its conclusion, as she was replaced in the leadership of the Nucleus when she was reassigned to another Secretariat. She reports that her successor did not carry out the activities with the same dedication and energy.

Subsequently, on October 20, 2017, a new operation was carried out that resulted in a conflict between the public security forces and the Senegalese migrant population. Unfortunately, once again, the news broadcasted by *Diário Popular* cannot be found on its website, although there is a post on the newspaper's Facebook page directing to the site, which, when accessed, presents an error stating that the news is nonexistent. However, this time, a video is accessible²⁰ that covers part of the operation. The video is two minutes and twenty-three seconds long, with the first few seconds capturing the sound of a stun gun being fired three times, accompanied by the image of an immobile migrant standing, leaning against a wall. The sound conveys a clear sense of turbulence, with the crowd shouting, "He's going to kill the guy!", "What's this for?!", "He was walking, not selling...". Immediately following the third stun gun discharge, the previously still migrant begins to move suddenly toward the police officer holding the yellow-colored weapon, at which point the confusion intensifies, along with the increase in shouting and movement. The number of four police officers involved in restraining the migrant can be counted, amid the failed attempts by two civilians to intervene. Shouts of insults directed at the police officers, both from men and women, can be heard in the background at this moment. Within seconds, the Senegalese man is handcuffed and taken away from the scene. The animosity between the police officers and the public becomes clear, with one moment at the beginning of the video showing a police officer harshly seeming to instruct a woman to move away, and later, right after the migrant is handcuffed, a man can be seen very close to a police officer, clearly attempting to intimidate him. A woman appears to try to calm the civilian down. At this moment, the Municipal Guards begin

²⁰ <https://www.facebook.com/diariopopularRS/videos/1797696666924960>

to leave the scene, accompanied by the crowd shouting "Cowards!" while clapping in a protest rhythm.

Em conversa com a atual Comandante da Guarda Municipal de Pelotas, Cíntia Lopes Aires, fui informado que a Guarda Municipal não realizava nesse momento a apreensão das mercadorias, sendo apenas responsável pela escolta e proteção dos servidores públicos fiscais, vinculados à Secretaria de Mobilidade da cidade. Tendo em vista a postura agressiva e ameaçadora que estavam recebendo por parte da população imigrante que labora no calçadão de forma irregular, a Prefeitura, por meio do representante do executivo da época, solicita a presença da Guarda Municipal durante as apreensões. De acordo com a Comandante, nos dias atuais, embora não se tenha notícias de abordagens violentas, a Guarda Municipal continua realizando a escolta dos fiscais, sendo que a estratégia de operação aplicada atualmente seja a chegada da Guarda Municipal no local de comércio de forma muito antecipada, anteriormente até mesmo dos próprios comerciantes. Assim, tais ação, de caráter preventivo, impede que os imigrantes ocupem os pontos importantes do cenário e, por sua vez, diminui as chances que possíveis embates aconteçam durante a fiscalização do centro da cidade.

We can thus observe three important cases of conflict, from one perspective, or police violence, from another, in the city where Senegalese individuals work/worked in the informal trade sector. The first occurred on December 2, 2015, the second on June 9, 2016, and the last on October 20, 2017. It is important to note that the research group GEMIGRA has been involved in immigrant care since the first of these operations. Professor Dr. Ana Paula Dittgen reports that after the Immigrant Care Plan, there was a noticeable decrease in the number of conflicts between municipal guards and immigrants, as well as a reduction in their intensity. It is also

impossible to find information regarding the termination of these operations, with the most recent news using the term dating back to June 14, 2017. Therefore, I conclude that it is a term difficult to apply, with few details regarding its origin, objectives, or conclusion. The most comprehensive news on such operations is precisely the one cited above, curiously the last one to be published²¹. When we examine the cases described above in detail, it is not difficult to think of Egon Bittner, when he classifies the police as “It makes much more sense to say that the police are nothing else than a mechanism for the distribution of situationally justified force in society” (1970, p. 39). In this way, we clearly address the situation in which the State is the legitimate holder of physical force. What occurs is a monopoly on the use of force and its legitimate demonstration before society.

Do not be mistaken, here we are talking about the control of specific parts of society, as, for instance, when Loïc Wacquant (2009) discusses the State’s management of misery and poverty in the United States. It is not accurate to say that Brazil has had an era of welfare state per se, but we can speak about a comparison in the management of poverty between countries. In Brazil, especially when discussing a post-abolition Brazil, where the freed individuals did not receive any historical reparations or compensation, it is no surprise that the lower class is predominantly composed of Black people. According to data from the IBGE in 2022²², the number of white people considered poor, 21 percent, was half the number of Black people considered poor in Brazil, 40 percent.

The racial and class hierarchy is the mark, and, therefore, the key of the discussions here. The shift from a welfare-oriented state to a system focused on

²¹ <https://www.diariopopular.com.br/geral/operacao-contra-a-venda-ilegal-124739/>?

²² This information can be consulted at the following website, but only in Portuguese: https://agenciadenoticias.ibge.gov.br/media/com_mediaibge/arquivos/070903d82038130a93f0374ada39f81d.pdf

policing and punishment, where addressing marginalization through criminalization and enforcing punitive control over disadvantaged groups becomes a form of social policy at the lower tiers of the class and racial hierarchy (Wacquant, 2009). Didier Fassin (2013) goes further when the topic is specifically the policing of immigrant bodies, establishing a logic of punishment as a form of disciplining these bodies.

Conclusions

The history of Pelotas demonstrates, through its formation, cultural and economic construction, the segregation of classes and race. The arrival of Senegalese immigrants, therefore, Africans with phenotypic traits of dark-skinned Black people, drew attention when they entered the territory of Pelotas.

At first, we might think of the arrival of the Senegalese as a new chapter for the city of Pelotas, a chapter of welcoming free African immigrants who finally arrive here of their own will, by choice, and in search of a better life.

In this sense, it is true, but when we think about police brutality, which is the focus of the research proposed here, we realize that we are not inaugurating a new, positive chapter for the city. We are repeating a grim facet of the past, of social exclusion based on class and race.

The reception of Senegalese immigrants, dark-skinned Black people, distinct from the Black population already present in the city, broke an unspoken rule about the spaces that Black bodies can occupy in the city and symbolically disturbed local society, which suggests that it triggered the cases of police brutality analyzed in this article.

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